

BRILL

BIJDRAGEN TOT DE TAAL-, LAND- EN
VOLKENKUNDE 181 (2025) 291–316

brill.com/bki

Book Reviews

Justito Adiprasetio, *Komunikasi dan Kuasa: Sejarah Pengkajian dan Ilmu Komunikasi dalam Diskursus Epistemik Indonesia*. Yogyakarta: Cantrik Pustaka, 2023, 324 pp. ISBN: 9786236063712, price: IDR 120,000.00 (paperback).

Many scholars have examined the connection between social science and power in the Indonesian context, from the Dutch colonial period to the fall of the Suharto regime (Hadiz & Dakidae 2005; Hanneman 1999). Several scholars have also explored the potential for decolonizing knowledge by analyzing the contributions of academics and public intellectuals who offer alternative frameworks for social understanding grounded in Indonesian perspectives (Akmaliah 2022; Fansuri 2014; Farid 2014; Goss 2011). Nevertheless, there has been some examination of the relationship between communication studies and power in Indonesia, including on the history of this field itself. Under Suharto's presidency, communication functioned as an academic discipline and a tool of political intervention, playing a crucial role in controlling public discourse and silencing criticism. Revoking a newspaper's permit for criticizing government policies is a prime example (Hill & Sen 2007; Sen & Hill 2010). In this context, Justito's work is valuable as it helps to initiate critical dialogue on this important issue.

Chapter 1 problematizes the field of communication studies from multiple perspectives and highlights the significance of the work by proposing an alternative approach. At the epistemological level, Justito engages with scholars who have analyzed the development of communication studies in the United States since the 1990s. These scholars question the historicity of the field and critique its limited engagement with social theories. At the discursive level, many have raised concerns over the field's failure to critically examine the interplay between politics and power, shaped by various stakeholders during that period. These two dimensions provide the foundation for Justito's self-reflexive approach to contextualizing communication studies in Indonesia. He argues that tracing the field's historical development in Indonesia, particularly

through the lens of socio-political influences, is a complex endeavor, largely due to the limited engagement of Indonesian scholars with this issue. As a result, communication studies in Indonesia have often been characterized as a relatively young discipline within the broader landscape of the social sciences.

The foundations of communication studies in Indonesia can be traced back to the period preceding and during Dutch colonial rule, particularly in the early encounters between colonizers and the colonized, and the subsequent phase of formal colonial domination. During this time, the field of *Indologie*, which focused on language and culture, emerged and later evolved into what is now recognized as communication studies following Indonesia's independence, as explored in Chapters 2 and 3. In these chapters, the author analyzes how Dutch colonialism employed a body of knowledge, comprised of data and information grounded in imperialist ideologies and rational modernity, to assert control over the Dutch East Indies, a society governed by different cultural logics. Focusing on Javanese society, the author contends that total colonization was hindered by the deeply rooted patron–client communication system known as *kawula–gusti* (pp. 51–54). This traditional structure posed a communicative dilemma: while Dutch colonial authorities exploited it to maintain dominance, their efforts at capital accumulation were frequently undermined by corruption among local rulers, or “little kings,” responsible for regional governance. Simultaneously, certain Javanese figures sought autonomy and national independence. However, their aspirations were often constrained by traditional Javanese cultural norms, as illustrated in the case of Kartini (pp. 75–76). Additionally, within the field of Indology, there was an early ambition to institutionalize the study of the region, which ultimately led to the establishment of the *Koninklijk Instituut voor Taal-, Land- en Volkenkunde* (KITLV) (p. 85).

The influence of Dutch colonization and its apparatus, including the institution of censorship through the state publishing body *Balai Pustaka*, came to an end during the brief but transformative period of Japanese occupation (1942–1945). This occupation significantly reconfigured existing power structures and communication strategies. Beyond replacing the colonial Dutch language with Malay, the Japanese administration introduced political knowledge into the public sphere by institutionalizing propaganda activities through the *Sendenbu* (Propaganda Department). This body not only organized various youth paramilitary political organizations and produced films, but also established numerous units that conducted propaganda campaigns in Javanese villages. These efforts promoted the concept of *Asia Raya* (Greater East Asia), positioning Japan as the central axis of regional power (p. 113).

Following independence, the institutional legacy of the *Sendenbu* persisted, albeit with different objectives, under Indonesia's first two presidencies, as discussed in Chapter 4. During Sukarno's presidency, the institution was transformed into the Ministry of Information, which served three principal functions: acting as the central government body for disseminating information to the public; protecting the nation from ideological infiltration via foreign information as part of a broader decolonization project; and enforcing censorship against mass media that criticized Sukarno's policies (pp. 128–135). The orientation of communication studies in Indonesia shifted notably between the Sukarno and Suharto administrations. While Suharto retained many of Sukarno's objectives for the Ministry of Information, his regime further embedded the ideology of development (*ideologi pembangunan*) within the state's information apparatus. This ideological shift marked a transformation in the genealogy of communication knowledge: from its earlier foundation in the German tradition of *Publizistik* during the 1950s to a more centralized adoption of the American social science paradigm of *komunikasi* by the 1970s (pp. 145–149). This transition was particularly evident in most Indonesian state universities, where the American model became dominant.

The fall of the Suharto regime offered a major opportunity for communication studies in Indonesia to shift from serving as a tool of authoritarian control to embracing critical approaches, including leftist perspectives and interdisciplinary approaches common in U.S. and European universities. However, Suharto's systematic eradication of leftist and communist influences, along with their intellectual foundations, has left such critical traditions—especially class analysis—largely absent from Indonesian academia (Farid 2005). Consequently, in the post-authoritarian era, communication studies have been predominantly shaped by market-oriented ideologies, driven by the rapid growth of media industries. This market-driven orientation is evident in the structure of curricula and the content of media studies courses at many Indonesian public universities, as demonstrated in Chapter 7 which is rigorously and systematically supported by tables and statistical data.

This book serves as an invaluable reference for scholars and students interested in communication studies and the intersection of social science and power in the Indonesian context. By comprehensively tracing the genealogy of communication studies—from the pre-colonial and colonial periods through the Sukarno and Suharto presidencies to the post-authoritarian era—Justito has successfully repositioned communication studies within a critical framework. His work also contributes to the decolonization of social science by reframing power relations in communication through the lens of the *kawula-*

gusti dynamic. One minor shortcoming is the absence of citation references on pages 56, 58, and 122, which could be addressed in a future revised edition.

Wahyudi Akmaliah

Department of Malay Studies, National University of Singapore, Singapore;
Research Centre for Society and Culture, National Research and Innovation
Agency (PMB-BRIN), Jakarta, Indonesia
wahyudi@u.nus.edu

References

- Akmaliah, W. (2022). Between Decolonization and Intellectual Nativism: Seeking the Indonesian Alternative Discourse on Social Sciences. *Southeast Asian Social Science Review*, 7(2), 31–55. [https://doi.org/10.29945/SEASSR.202205_7\(2\).0002](https://doi.org/10.29945/SEASSR.202205_7(2).0002)
- Fansuri, H. (2014). *Sosiologi Indonesia: Diskursus Kekuasaan dan Reproduksi Pengetahuan*. LP3S.
- Farid, H. (2005). The class question in Indonesian Social Sciences. In V. Hadiz & D. Dakidae (Eds.), *Social Science and Power in Indonesia*. Equinox Publishing.
- Farid, H. (2014). *Rewriting the Nation: Pramoedya Ananta Toer and the Politics of Decolonisation*. National University of Singapore.
- Goss, A. (2011). *The Floracrats: State-Sponsored Science and the Failure of the Enlightenment in Indonesia*. The University of Wisconsin Press.
- Hadiz, V., & Dakidae, D. (2005). *Social Science and Power in Indonesia*. Equinox Publishing.
- Hanneman, S. (1999). *The Development of Sociology in Indonesia: The Production of Knowledge, State Formation and Economic Change*. Swinburne University of Technology.
- Hill, D.T., & Sen, K. (2007). *Media, Culture, and Politics in Indonesia*. Equinox Publishing.
- Sen, K., & Hill, D.T. (2010). Politics and the media in twenty-first century Indonesia: Decade of democracy. In *Politics and the Media in Twenty-First Century Indonesia: Decade of Democracy*. Routledge Taylor & Francis Group. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203840429>